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UDC: 575.22.631.4/92.664.-4

FOOD SAFETY: GLOBAL PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. Food safety is one of the most critical global issues facing humanity today. The constant increase in population, climate change, and globalization have exacerbated food safety concerns. In this paper, we discuss the global challenges related to food safety, focusing on contamination risks, climate change, the role of food additives, and modern technologies used in food processing. Additionally, solutions to these problems are proposed, with a focus on sustainability, innovative practices, and the implementation of global standards such as HACCP, GMP, ISO, and others to ensure the safety and quality of food products.

Key words: food safety, global issues, food additives, quality, standards, climate change, sustainability, HACCP, ISO

Introduction. Food safety is about ensuring that all people have access to sufficient and quality food. This issue has become one of the global challenges today, leading to economic, social, and environmental risks for many countries. The food safety problem is related to population growth, climate change, economic inequalities, and technological development. To ensure food safety, global actions and strategies are required. [1,2,3] Food safety is a critical and multifaceted global issue, with various causes and factors. Studying these factors, developing scientifically grounded solutions, and innovative approaches is essential for future generations and the general well-being of nature. [3,5] Today, this is a duty and responsibility for all of us. In a market economy, prioritizing eco-friendly products can serve as a strong economic incentive for their production. [3,5,12] The processing of agricultural products refers to natural or processed products consumed by humans (including baby food, dietary foods), food raw materials of plant, animal,

microbiological, and artificial origin, and water, plant, animal, microbiological, mineral substances, dairy and meat products, and seafood used in the production of food products. These products form a specific structure in the human body, satisfying the body's needs for various vitamins and minerals in addition to providing a sense of satiety. [3,5,11]

Methods and Materials. This article analyzes the global food safety issues and the proposed solutions to combat them. The data is derived from global organizations and scientific research. The method used to analyze existing studies and reports is based on statistical data published by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the World Health Organization (WHO), and other international organizations. The comparative analysis method involves assessing the differences between historical and modern situations. The expert evaluation method includes interviews with experts and

professionals who propose solutions to food safety issues.

Today, there are 5,000 types of pesticides and chemical ingredients available. Their use in agriculture has increased tenfold, and crop loss due to insects has doubled over the past 50 years. The increase in pesticides has led to the development of 650 types of pests resistant to some of these toxins. [6,7] Every day, people around the world suffer from pesticide poisoning. These are chemical substances that pollute the air, soil, water, and products, causing over a million poisonings annually. Chemical hazards are defined as "chemicals accidentally introduced into food products that may compromise their safety or suitability." [3,4,9] Pesticides are chemical substances used to improve soil, combat weeds, insects, and rodents, and protect crops from mold and fungi. The European Union has started to implement unified standards for assessing the risks of chemicals in food and introduced other common labels for food safety. [1,11]

It is well known that many pesticides are harmful to health and have carcinogenic properties; however, until now, consumers cannot determine from the label how much of these harmful substances are present in the purchased products. In developed countries, consumers typically have the option to choose between "organic" (chemically-free) products or regular products. The price difference is significant, and the choice of "organic" products is not as common as purchasing regular products. According to the standards of the Codex Alimentarius Commission and the European Union, by September 1, 2020, the adoption of the "Supply Chain Safety Management Systems" ISO 28000 international standards series was required. Within three months, all enterprises and organizations involved in the agricultural and food product value chain must undergo an evaluation to ensure compliance with the ISO 28000 international standard. [3,5] This is a series of measures, and each producer, including those involved in the storage and processing of agricultural products, must ensure the naturalness and quality of the products. According to global standards, Global Gap, and other standard requirements, the agronomic

practices and technologies used in the production, storage, and processing of products must ensure that the use of chemical and mineral substances does not exceed the permitted amounts, with an emphasis on quality rather than quantity, ensuring strict consistency in volume. Naturally, the use of natural and environmentally clean methods in processing raises the product's cost. In this regard, consumer demand may vary. Especially for low-income populations, the price of natural and high-quality products may be more important than food safety. Disruptions in ecological balance, losses in the flora and fauna world, and the disappearance of natural and local species as a result of the development of genetic engineering are being observed. [10,12] For the future, resources need to be preserved. This requires the rational use of existing resources, drinking water, clean air, and natural minerals, saving them, and valuing their true worth. In this regard, various research, innovative proposals, scientifically based ideas, initiatives, and concrete solutions are crucial on a global scale.

Chemical and natural additives used in the food industry enhance the attractiveness, shelf life, and quality of products. However, the constant intake of these substances into the human body raises a common concern about the potential risks they pose. Food additives, both natural and artificial (synthetic), extend the shelf life of food products or give them specific characteristics. The use of food additives (such as vinegar and lactic acid, table salt, certain spices, and others) dates back thousands of years. [12,13] However, it was only in the 19th-20th centuries that special attention began to be given to them. The European Union has developed a system for digital codification of food additives to harmonize their use.

The system is approved by FAO-WHO. Dioxins and dioxin-like substances are foreign compounds released into living organisms as products or by-products of a range of technologies. These substances have been continuously produced by humanity over the past half-century, released into the environment, and accumulated there. Dioxins have never been a targeted product of human activity, only accompanying it as micro contaminants. Dioxins could be one of the causes of long-term pollution

of the biosphere. Like physical, biological, and chemical hazards, they can enter food products at any stage of production.

The risk of harming the consumer's health is low for most foreign substances, as only a few may be sharp or harsh enough to cause physical harm. However, in any case, it is unpleasant for a consumer to find foreign substances in food. This risk is far more serious compared to contamination by other highly toxic substances in the environment. These numbers (codes) are used along with the names of functional classes that reflect the group of food additives by technological functions (subclasses). The letter "E" and the identification number have a specific interpretation, indicating that the safety of a particular substance has been tested, there are recommendations for its technological requirements for use in food additives, and purity standards have been established for this substance. After some E-numbers (the letter "E" followed by a three-digit number), there are small letters, such as E160—carotenoids, and others. The presence of food additives in food products must be indicated on the label. In such cases, the additive can be identified either as an individual substance or as a representative of a functional class along with its E number, such as sodium benzoate or preservative E211. According to the recommended numerical codification system, additives are classified by purpose as follows (only the main groups): E100-E182—coloring agents; E200—preservatives; E300—antioxidants; E400—stabilizers; E500—emulsifiers; E600—flavor enhancers and flavors; E700-E800—reserve indices; E900—glazing agents, bread improvers.

Results. The global food safety issues and their main causes include climate change—drought, water shortages, and natural disasters disrupting food supply systems. People's economic condition—rising prices, food product costs, and distribution problems. If simple technological solutions are applied, their effectiveness lies in the long-term storage of food products and improving food supply systems by utilizing advanced technologies. Social stability—ensuring food safety for the population through health, education, and social protection. For mixed food products, safety

indicators (excluding microbiological indicators) are determined based on the mass fractions and safety indicators for these components, taking into account the contribution of individual components as specified in the technical regulation. Suppliers of dehydrated food products calculate these based on the original food (raw material) depending on the content of solids in the product and dehydrated food. The presence of pathogens causing infectious and parasitic diseases, as well as toxins that are dangerous to human and animal health, is not allowed in food products in circulation. The shelf life and storage conditions of food products are determined by the manufacturer. Packaging materials in contact with food products and materials used in the production of products must meet the requirements set out in the relevant technical regulation of the Customs Union. The requirements for food additives, flavors, and technological agents used in food production are defined by the relevant technical regulations of the Customs Union. GMO (genetically modified organism) food raw materials from plant, animal, and microbial origin should only be used in food production if they come from GMO lines that are registered with the state. If the manufacturer does not use GMOs in food production, a GMO content of 0.9% or less in the food product is considered an accidental or technically unavoidable contamination, and such food products are not considered as containing GMOs. For fortified food products, the content of each food or biologically active substance used for fortification should be brought to a consumption level of 100 ml or 100 g, or a single portion of such products should constitute at least 5% of the daily intake. The content of probiotic microorganisms in fortified food products should be such that the product contains at least 10^9 colony-forming units (microbial cells) per 1 g or 1 ml of the product.

The use of GMO-containing food raw materials in the production of food products for children, pregnant women, and breastfeeding women is not allowed. The use of food raw materials obtained with the use of pesticides in food products for children is also prohibited. Additionally, the following requirements must be met: cookies for children's food should not

contain more than 25% sugar; baked products for children's food should not contain more than 0.5% salt; the content of ethyl alcohol should not exceed 0.2%; natural coffee; apricot kernel seeds; vinegar; sweeteners, and special dietary foods for therapeutic and prophylactic nutrition, except for women's milk substitutes, should not have trans isomers of fatty acids making up more than 4% of the total fatty acid content. In the production of food products derived from animals, the slaughter of animals is carried out in specially designated areas for this purpose. Slaughterhouses and production facilities for meat and meat products must adhere to hygiene and veterinary-sanitary requirements for the storage and use of production facilities. These requirements are aimed at ensuring the production of safe food and non-food products, as well as preventing the occurrence of unacceptable risks.

Discussion. Global economic changes, ecological imbalances, and modernization and innovative approaches in agriculture have, in some cases, exacerbated food security issues. In this regard, the following solutions exist:

1. **Climate-adaptive agricultural strategies** – Agricultural policies adapted to climate change are proving effective in many countries. Natural disasters such as drought, water scarcity, and water-related disasters are significantly impacting food security. Climate change causes imbalances in the delivery of food products between countries, especially in regions suffering from desertification and water scarcity. These issues negatively affect agricultural production.
2. **Price increases, lack of raw material bases, and local economic conditions** – Rising prices, lack of raw materials, and local economic conditions make it difficult for populations to access food. In low-income countries, food demand is relatively low, and people face problems obtaining sufficient and quality food.
3. **Pesticides, fumigants, and bacterial diseases** – The use of pesticides, fumigants, and the presence of

bacterial diseases degrade the quality of food products, which, in turn, harms the supply chains.

4. **Technological and social infrastructure underdevelopment** – In certain regions, problems arise in food production due to underdeveloped technologies and social infrastructure.
5. **Population growth** – With the increasing global population, food production and distribution become even more challenging. The growing urban population complicates rural agriculture and production, leading to lower-quality and more complex farming practices.
6. **Urbanization and demand for food** – The rise in urban populations increases the demand for food, but managing supply chains becomes more difficult. Disruptions in food trade and supply systems (such as pandemics, blockages) affect international trade and global supply chains, making production and distribution systems more complicated.
7. **The use of modern technologies** in the food industry determines the quality of products. However, due to the factors and reasons mentioned above, the naturalness and safety of food remain under question.
8. **From this perspective**, the rational use of local and medicinal plants is essential. It is important to process agricultural products while preserving their natural qualities. To address the mentioned issues, it is necessary to develop both external and internal trade relations. According to geographical location, suitable plants should be cultivated. The storage and processing of agricultural products should be carried out as naturally as possible. In this regard, working with GLOBAL.G.A.P, GMP, ISO, HACCP, and HALAL standards will yield the necessary results.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be emphasized that any technology must serve the health of humans and the preservation of nature. Solutions to global problems can vary. The food

additives used in production should not only improve product quality but also maintain their beneficial properties. To achieve this, cultivation and processing must be carried out within the framework of standard requirements. By 2050, the world's population is projected to reach nearly 10 billion. This, in turn, will increase the demand for food. Changing weather conditions, extreme events, and rising temperatures threaten crops. The shortage of resources may lead to disruptions in the processing industry. The reduction of arable land, water scarcity, and soil degradation pose major challenges for agriculture. Food resources are unevenly distributed across the world, and food is not

always sufficient for all regions. Political instability and conflicts also disrupt food production and distribution systems. Solving these problems requires a comprehensive approach that includes sustainable farming practices, technological innovations, effective policies, and global cooperation.

Acknowledgements: I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the Department of Agricultural Products Storage and Processing at the Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies, as well as the professors and teachers of the Faculty of Food Chemistry at Andijan State University, for their valuable assistance and support in writing this article.

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